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NLRP7 exerts specific control of genes associated with pluripotency.

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NLRP7 exerted specific control of genes associated with pluripotency including embryogenesis genes involved in the transformation including TACSTD2 (Trop-2), as well as other molecules associated with pluripotency encoded by the TNRC and GPRC families.